

Title: A transitivity-based exploration of a wrongful conviction for arson and murder: The case of Kristine Bunch

Short title: Transitivity-based exploration of a wrongful conviction

Abstract:

With more and more wrongful convictions emerging, it is evident their occurrence is reaching global heights (cf. Garrett 2011). Well-known cases (e.g. Central Park Five, Steven Avery, Amanda Knox), although merely the tip of the iceberg, serve to highlight the flaws inherent in justice systems worldwide. Many innocent people are having their freedom taken away without reason. One such case is that of Kristine Bunch, who was wrongfully convicted of arson and murdering her son, resulting in her wrongful imprisonment for 17 years. To examine how Kristine represents her miscarriage of justice discursively, I examine the transitivity patterns (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014) present in a semi-structured interview with her and, in doing so, aim to create awareness of some probable key language processes in wrongful convictions more generally.

Keywords: *exoneration, family support, innocence, Kristine Bunch, legal support, oral narrative, prison life, transitivity, tunnel vision, wrongful convictions*

1. Introduction

In recent years, we have witnessed a steady rise in acknowledging the number of times that an innocent person has found themselves wrongfully accused (cf. Leo 2009: 332) and, subsequently, wrongfully convicted for a crime or, sometimes, an event that never was a crime to begin with. The latter was the case for exoneree Kristine Bunch (hereafter Kristine), as we will see in this paper.

From the moment we are born, police have, as a key aspect of their mission, to keep the community safe from the “bad guys”. Likewise, there is a general assumption that, once a case reaches court, the prosecution will also do everything in its power to ensure that the judge and jury in question will send only the “bad guys” to jail. For this reason, it is difficult to conceive that, on more occasions than is widely anticipated, it is actually these same individuals who are contributing to a failing in our justice system, by sending innocent people to prison.

With an increased recognition of wrongful convictions as a somewhat common occurrence (cf. Norris et al. 2017: 598), causes of such convictions have received increased research attention. This research has primarily derived from the law and criminology sectors, in which scholars who specialise in specific areas of the justice system (cf. Drizin & Colgan 2004; Leo 2008, 2009; Redlich 2010; Garrett 2011; Clow et al. 2012; Clow & Leach 2015) or defence lawyers who have had clients that have been let down by the justice system, attempt to identify the primary reasons leading to wrongful convictions¹ (cf. Bonventre 2020; Johnson 2020). From this research, what emerge as the main causes are the following: (i) eyewitness misidentification (cf. Gross et al. 2005; Pezdek 2012), whereby an allegedly credible witness mistakenly claims to have seen the accused at the scene of the crime; (ii) false confessions (cf. Rizzelli 2019; Scherr et al. 2020), whereby especially young and vulnerable people when accused of a crime find themselves falsely confessing after being fed false promises by the police that they will not be in any trouble or will be able to go home once they tell the police what they want to hear; (iii) false guilty pleas (cf. Henderson & Levitt 2018), whereby many innocent people find themselves terrified of the consequences of being found (wrongfully) guilty and, therefore, prefer to

¹ This list of causes has been cited by the Innocence Network comprising numerous Innocence Projects worldwide, including Innocence Canada (<https://www.innocencecanada.com/causes-of-wrongful-convictions/>), The Innocence Project in New York (<https://innocenceproject.org/>) and the California Innocence Project (<https://californiainnocenceproject.org/>), to name but a few.

exert some control over their fate themselves and, to do so, choose to plead guilty to ensure a lighter sentence; (iv) jailhouse informant testimony (cf. Warden 2004; Natapoff 2009), which is notably problematic in wrongful conviction cases with figures revealing that around 45% of innocent prisoners who have been on death row and since exonerated were originally convicted as a result of the testimony given by people already serving time in prison; (v) professional misconduct (cf. Covey 2012), in which either the police during the investigation phase or, subsequently, the prosecution team in the lead up to and during trial fabricate evidence in order to convict an innocent person; (vi) tunnel vision (cf. Findley 2012; Brants 2013; Reichart 2016), also referred to as confirmation bias, which occurs when the police form a belief which they adhere to and then proceed to search for evidence that will fit that preconceived belief (Garrett 2011: 266); (vii) systemic discrimination (cf. Huff et al. 1996; Bell 2015: 24), in which an innocent person is found guilty on the grounds of their gender, race or ethnicity; (viii) perjury (cf. Christianson 2004; Pezdek 2012), in which, often, experts lie at trial; and (ix) faulty forensics (cf. Thompson 2008; Cole 2012) or, as exoneree Roy Brown effectively explains, “Junk science sent me to prison” (Garrett 2011: 89). It is important to acknowledge that although these factors undoubtedly contribute to the prevalence of wrongful convictions (Gould & Leo 2010), they nonetheless all have one thing in common, which is the potential for human error. Thus, wrongful convictions may well be more likely to occur when any one of these issues arises in a case, but that is not to say that wrongful convictions are limited to the aforementioned causes.

Increased research attention is also evident in forensic linguistics. For example, lying (cf. Simpson 1992; Heffer 2020; Marsili 2020), police interview techniques when interrogating suspects (cf. Heydon 2005; Haworth 2012) and courtroom language (cf. Danet 1980; Felton Rosulek 2010) have all been examined, although not on a large scale for cases of wrongful conviction. That said, one of the main causes of wrongful convictions, false confessions, has been explored from a linguistic perspective (cf. Grebler 2005; Rizzelli 2019). Rizzelli (2019), for instance, explored the linguistic features of a set of confessions now known to be false and a set of confessions that have never been in dispute. According to Rizzelli (2019), we are yet to encounter a method for identifying false confessions, with studies to date having focused on the similarities in content of confessions. In her own study, she notes that the use of personal and impersonal pronouns, as well as the structure *I + lexical verb* revealed differences across the two corpora in question. More specifically, Rizzelli (2019) observed that a high frequency of impersonal pronouns was found to mean a higher likelihood of the confession being false; meanwhile, the texts comprising more conjunctions and personal pronouns were found to be more common among those confessions not in dispute. A further difference was the use of *I + lexical verb*, with this structure seemingly less prevalent in false confessions by comparison to those not in dispute. Thus, Rizzelli's (2019) findings would suggest that linguistic differences may be an indication of the legitimacy of a confession and, thus, provide information which could be born in mind by police when retrieving confessions in future investigations. Research such as Rizzelli's (2019), therefore, not only serves to expand our knowledge of the language of real and false confessions, but may also assist with reducing the chances of a future miscarriage of justice.

Surprisingly, research has not so far explored recounts of experience by the wrongfully convicted themselves, but such work has the potential to raise awareness of wrongful convictions more generally, as well as to understand how they occur; that is, who better to tell communities how the justice system can make mistakes than those who have experienced an injustice, and help us understand how these mistakes can impact the life of an innocent person, as well as those directly or indirectly involved in the case (e.g. the family of the wrongfully convicted). Within the existing literature in criminology and law, there are examples of exonerees who have told their story (cf. Clow & Leach 2015; Makani 2018); however, the current study differs in its specific aim to provide an exploratory analysis of the transitivity patterns used by, in this case, Kristine, in order to allow her story to be heard and, equally, to show how, linguistically, she represents herself and her miscarriage of justice. Significantly, there are several related research studies in which the testimonies of activists against the apartheid in South Africa in the 1980s have been analysed for transitivity patterns (cf. Bock & Duncan 2006; Bock 2009; Hattingh 2011), providing a range of findings. Bock (2009), for instance, notes that from her transitivity

analysis of the testimony given by activist Colin de Souza, there are clear signs of agency on the part of the narrator: that is, de Souza portrays himself as someone who does things, and who makes things happen, as opposed to the one who is impacted by the actions of others. Meanwhile, Hattingh (2011) finds that other testimonies from activists construe themselves as the affected participant in material, mental and verbal clauses.

Given the comparable nature of the discourse under analysis in this paper to the aforementioned testimonies, a transitivity analysis of the semi-structured interview with Kristine, as someone who was wrongfully imprisoned and only exonerated 17 years later, is expected to (i) contribute to our understanding of how wrongful convictions come about in the first place; and (ii) increase one's understanding of how the lives of an exoneree, such as Kristine or other innocent people like her, perceive the events and participants involved in those events and how they are impacted by their miscarriage of justice.

2. Theoretical background

Language can serve as a way for us to make sense of our internal and external experiences and, thus, according to systemic functional linguists, is said to be a system of meaning-making (cf. Halliday & Matthiessen 2014: 27); that is, Systemic Functional Grammar (hereafter SFG) facilitates an exploration of why, when using language, we opt for certain linguistic choices in favour of other potential alternatives and, in doing so, allows critical discourse analysts to reflect on the ideological choices that people subconsciously make when communicating through language. SFG further asserts that there are three language metafunctions, namely the interpersonal metafunction, the textual metafunction and the ideational metafunction. Together, these draw on a set of lexicogrammatical patterns that can serve to construe human experience (Halliday 1985: 53). However, unlike the textual and interpersonal metafunctions, the ideational metafunction comprises two subcomponents, commonly referred to as the logical and experiential metafunctions. It is the latter we are concerned with in this paper given that transitivity represents "the experiential component of the grammar of the clause" (Halliday & Webster 2014: 25) and serves to linguistically realise our experience. According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), the transitivity system features three main components: (i) process types, (ii) participant roles, and (iii) circumstantial elements. Each of these components contributes meaning to the clause, although not necessarily at the same level. That is, whilst process types and participant roles are classed as central to the clause realisation, circumstances adopt a more peripheral position in the clause, by offering optional additional information. Furthermore, as they are, "unlike participants, not directly involved in the process" (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014: 221), they often carry the same meaning across clauses, thereby occurring "freely in all types of process" (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014: 310). As the two core components of the transitivity system and those which are examined in this paper, Tables 1 and 2 below list the process and participant categories and subcategories as proposed by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014).

Major/Minor	Process category	Process subcategories			
Major types	Material	Creative	Transformative		
	Mental	Cognitive	Desiderative	Emotive	Perceptive
	Relational	Attributive: Intensive Possessive Circumstantial	Identifying: Intensive Possessive Circumstantial		
Minor types	Verbal				
	Behavioural				
	Existential				

Table 1. Process types (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014)²

Process types	Participant roles					
Material	<i>Actor</i>	<i>Goal</i>	<i>Beneficiary:</i> - <i>Recipient</i> - <i>Client</i>	<i>Scope</i>	<i>Initiator</i>	<i>Attribute</i>
Mental	<i>Senser</i>	<i>Phenomenon</i>	<i>Inducer</i>			
Relational: Attributive	<i>Carrier</i>	<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Attributor</i>			
Relational: Identifying	<i>Identifier</i>	<i>Identified</i>	<i>Assigner</i>			
Verbal	<i>Sayer</i>	<i>Verbiage</i>	<i>Receiver</i>	<i>Target</i>		
Behavioural	<i>Behaver</i>	<i>Behaviour</i>				
Existential	<i>Existent</i>					

Table 2. Participant configurations across process types (Halliday & Matthiessen 2014)³

To recall, one of the fundamental aims of applying a transitivity analysis to Kristine’s discourse is to gain insights into how wrongful convictions come about and who better to listen to linguistically than someone who has first-hand experience of this. A transitivity analysis, in particular, has been carried out on this dataset because the application of this SFL framework can serve to inform our understanding of the speaker’s ideological standpoint, simply from how s/he organizes information at clause level, as well as invite “a consideration of power, control and agency” (Footitt 2002: 89). Thus, through examining the grammatical and lexical choices that Kristine makes when discussing her wrongful conviction and, more specifically, identifying the process types and participant roles that appear to dominate her discourse, we can acquire a good understanding of how she construes her experience of being let down by the justice system; that is, a transitivity analysis can (i) reveal who Kristine holds responsible for what she went through, (ii) shed light on how she feels about herself as well as others who, in one way or another, were involved in her case, and (iii) can draw our attention to the impact of a wrongful conviction on a person and not just whilst s/he is wrongfully imprisoned, but potentially for years or decades afterwards or in the worst case, the rest of their life.

² Whilst there are two subcategories of Relational processes, each of these also have further subtypes: Relational intensive, Relational possessive, and Relational circumstantial clauses (see Halliday & Matthiessen 2014: 263-279 for further detail).

³ Although only a brief description of the participant types is provided in this paper, detailed descriptions of each role can be found in Halliday and Matthiessen (2014).

3. Methodology

3.1. Background to the case of Kristine Bunch

Kristine, an exoneree from Indiana is, unfortunately, one of many betrayed by the US justice system. In a semi-structured interview, Kristine describes the details of her experience of being wrongfully convicted of arson and murder in 1996 and, consequently, wrongfully imprisoned for 17 years. It is likely that many people will think, just as I did myself at one time, that although terrible miscarriages of justice can undoubtedly occur, cases such as Kristine will by no means be frequent; however, this it seems is not the case. Wrongful convictions are an extensive problem, both in the US and on a global scale. Educated estimates suggest that between 3-4% of people serving jail time in the US alone are languishing in prison for a non-crime or a crime that they themselves never committed (cf. Simon 2012: 4). Though this interview with Kristine examines just one case, we can (i) draw linguistic attention to the nature of wrongful convictions and, (ii) begin to understand the impact on the lives of exonerees and their families. As Kristine herself said, "There is no justice for anyone if someone is wrongfully convicted. It only creates more victims".

In the case of Kristine, the events that would ultimately lead to her wrongful conviction began to unfold on the evening of June 29th, 1995. Kristine had spent an ordinary evening with her three-year-old son. They had eaten pizza at a neighbour's house before heading home to have a bath and watch some television. Sometime later, they both fell asleep. The following morning, Kristine awoke to discover that her house was on fire and that she couldn't get into her son's bedroom to rescue him. Sadly, he had died during that night and Kristine, very understandably, was left devastated and inconsolable. However, Kristine's nightmare at this point had only just started. A short time later, Kristine came under investigation by the local police and, following faulty forensic science together with a falsified fire report, Kristine was at the centre of an arson and murder trial. Subsequently, she was wrongfully convicted and sentenced to 50 years for arson and 60 years for the murder of her child, with both sentences to be served concurrently.

3.2. Dataset

For the purposes of this research paper, a semi-structured interview was carried out with Kristine. According to Adams (2015: 493), a semi-structured interview will usually last about an hour and, when conducted as a conversation with one respondent, allows for "a blend of closed- and open-ended questions, often accompanied by follow-up why or how questions" (ibid). Semi-structured interview questions are "open-ended in order to create a space for participants to narrate their experiences" (Cross & Galletta 2013: 47) with the aim of the interviewer/researcher being "to guide a participant in conveying an account of an experience as it relates to the topic of study" (ibid). Furthermore, a semi-structured interview approach allows an interviewee to "delve into totally unforeseen issues" (Adams 2015: 493). Given that the principal idea of this paper is to examine how, through her discourse, Kristine represents her miscarriage of justice, it seemed paramount to create this type of setting to encourage a free-rein discussion and, thus, enable Kristine to provide as little or as much detail as she wished to about her wrongful conviction and focus on the aspects that she wished to recount.

As is common practice for semi-structured interviews, formal consent was acquired from Kristine before the interview took place. In line with the semi-structured interview design, the majority of questions posed to Kristine were also open-ended and, excluding the word count for questions, Kristine's responses alone resulted in a final word count of just over 15,000 words. The clauses, as defined in the SFG framework, were then analysed for transitivity patterns in order to explore how Kristine represents her experience of being wrongfully convicted.

3.3. Methodology

The interview with Kristine was carried out using the online platform Zoom. This was to enable a recording of the interview, with Kristine's informed consent and, thus, a subsequent transcription of the dataset. Prior to the transcription phase, all participants mentioned by Kristine in the interview were allocated a three or four-digit code⁴ to ensure anonymity of all those indirectly involved. Once participant codes had been established and the interview transcribed, the interview transcript was saved as a .txt document that could subsequently be uploaded to the UAM Corpus Tool 5.0o (O'Donnell 2020) and a manual transitivity analysis was carried out. It is worthwhile mentioning that, although the UAM Corpus Tool provides the possibility to implement an automated annotation of transitivity patterns in a given dataset, thus saving a notable amount of time, a manual transitivity scheme was instead introduced here for two reasons: (i) to ensure that all potential analysis errors are my own and (ii) to implement some changes to Halliday and Matthiessen's (2014) transitivity model⁵ as it stands, for the purposes of striving to conduct a critical discourse analysis relevant to my purposes. These changes include (i) reducing the list of verbs in the behavioural process category and introducing the distinction put forward by Neale (2002) regarding an agentive and non-agentive *Senser*, to cater for instances of behavioural processes that distinguish between conscious and unconscious mental (primarily cognition and perception) activity (e.g. see vs. watch; hear vs. listen); and (ii) introducing the option to select more than one process type at a time⁶ as an attempt to conduct a more delicate CDA of the text in question. As many readers will be aware, there are differing views on how a transitivity analysis should be applied in terms of whether a grammatical or semantic analysis should be prioritised (cf. O'Donnell et al. 2008; Gwilliams & Fontaine 2015). Therefore, in implementing the abovementioned changes to the transitivity framework, the intention here is to minimise certain discrepancies where possible and, in doing so, maximise the potential to capture linguistic meanings.

Following a manual annotation of the transitivity patterns in Kristine's discourse, quantitative findings were retrieved from the UAM Corpus tool to determine which of the realms of experience Kristine focuses on the most and what this can tell us about the way in which she represents not only what she went through, but also those who were either fighting on her behalf or otherwise responsible for or implicated in this miscarriage of justice. Thus, the research questions (hereafter RQ) posed in this paper are:

(RQ1) What does an analysis of the transitivity patterns in Kristine's discourse reveal about how she represents herself?

(RQ2) Which participant roles does Kristine assign to others who, in one way or another, were involved or accountable for her wrongful conviction?

4. Results and Discussion

The results and discussion section has been divided into two subsections, with each addressing one research question.

⁴ To distinguish between speakers and those who were spoken about, three-digit codes were applied to the former, whilst four-digit codes were applied to the latter.

⁵ These changes are a work-in-progress and I would argue that substantial more data needs to be analysed before any definitive alterations to the transitivity framework can be put forward.

⁶ To cater for the annotation of more than one process simultaneously, the category "complex process" is introduced here.

4.1. What do the transitivity patterns in Kristine's discourse reveal about how she represents herself?

To answer this initial question, the most logical starting point is to explore the quantitative findings for the transitivity process types encountered in Kristine's discourse overall. From there, it will then be possible to take a closer look at which realms of experience come to the forefront whilst Kristine narrates her experience. An initial glance at the frequency of each of the transitivity process types in Kristine's discourse can be found in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Transitivity patterns in the discourse of Kristine

Figure 1 reveals that material processes are the most common type selected in Kristine's discourse, consistent with the fact that, together with relational processes, they are known to be the most frequent types in discourse more generally (cf. Halliday & Matthiessen 2014: 300). Nonetheless, to address RQ1 in more detail, we explore the distribution of participant roles that she assigns herself in her use of material processes. What emerges is that Kristine appears as the *Actor* (i.e. the doer) of a material process in 54.7% of cases. Two examples⁷ of this are provided in (1) and (2) below.

(1) [...] And they wanted to know everything that I **did** the night before. And, so I **went** through, you know, the whole spiel – “I **came** home from school, I **went** over to <<FBAU>>'s⁸. We had pizza for dinner with <<FBAU>>. I **got out** the lawnmower and I mowed <<FBAU>>'s yard and <<FBAT>>⁹ was out there with me – he had a little bubble mower – and so we mowed the yard, and then we went up to our house and we mowed the yard together. And then, you know, we took a bath together and did some laundry and he didn't really wanna settle down and go to sleep. And it was really hot. And so, I said, “You know what I'm **just gonna take** the day off tomorrow and we'll just sleep in.” And we fell asleep on the couch – I **read** him a book and we watched some T.V. And it's, I mean it's normal – I think. [...]

(2) [...] So I **went** towards his bedroom, and I couldn't see in there. And I saw fire on the floor in the doorway. And so I **picked up** a pillow and a blanket and I **tried to smother** it because I remembered hearing something that you could smother flames and they would go out. And that

⁷ When referred to in examples, processes appear in bold, whilst participant types appear in underlined italics.

⁸ <<FBAU>> is the code assigned to Kristine's neighbour for anonymity purposes.

⁹ <<FBAT>> is the code assigned to Kristine's first son for anonymity purposes.

absolutely didn't happen – the pillow and the blanket just melted in my hands. And, of course, I'm looking towards where I know his bed is and I think I see him and I feel like, you know, he's right there I just **have to get in** that room and I have to, I **have to get** him. And so I think that I hear him, and I think that I see him, but I **can't get in** through that doorway. So, I **run out** and I'm screaming for my neighbours, and I **pick up** his tricycle and I **bust out** his windows and I **start to climb** through, and at that time my neighbours pulled me out of the window because the flames had shot through the roof and told me that I **couldn't go back in** there, I **had to wait** for the fire department to get there. I **tried to run** back in the front door, and they held me back and one of the statements said that somebody smacked me because I **wouldn't stop fighting** them and **trying to get back in** there. [...]

As evidenced in the abovementioned examples, Kristine places herself in *Actor* position whilst narrating these events as she responds to the second question of the interview: "In your own words and as much or as little detail as you'd like to give, can you tell me what happened?" As a woman who was innocent of any wrongdoing, naturally she describes her attempts, to no avail, to save her son's life. Thus, the above examples show that it is not merely a question of Kristine citing herself as the *Actor* of material clauses; rather, through this resource, she represents herself as acting to extinguish the fire and act in ways that are not what might be expected of someone who is trying to kill her son.

To take this initial finding a step further, we investigated whether Kristine assigned herself the role of *Actor* more or less frequently at particular points of her narrative. Thus, the different time periods of the case as discussed by Kristine were first identified (see Figure 2 below). Subsequently, the number of times that Kristine cited herself as *Actor* when discussing each time period was extracted. These findings are also presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Kristine assigned the role of *Actor*

As evidenced above, Kristine appears to place herself in *Actor* position more often in specific stages of her case. Particularly notable is the fact that Kristine most often cites herself as *Actor* when discussing her time in prison, with three times as many instances emerging by comparison to when she discusses

her arrest. However, the wordcount for each section also varies considerably and must be taken into account. Thus, Table 3 provides details regarding the word count of each section of Kristine’s discourse, together with the % that each, thereby, corresponds to, and the number (and corresponding %) of material processes she employs at each stage.

Stage of discourse	Word count (raw)	Word count (%)	Material processes (raw)	Material processes (%)
Narrative of fire	1732	12.5	124	15.4
Suspicion / Under arrest	1887	13.6	112	13.9
Lead up to trial	2882	20.8	76	9.5
Time in prison	5444	39.3	352	43.8
Release from prison	1908	13.8	139	17.3

Table 3. Proportion of material processes to word count in each discourse section

To now examine some of these findings in more detail, we shall focus on those time periods when material processes were more dominant in her discourse (i.e. her time in prison and her subsequent release). When examining particular instances, we encounter a range of examples in the discourse which refer to the activities that Kristine immersed herself in whilst incarcerated, as exemplified in (3) and (4) below. As we can see, these were predominantly a means of survival for Kristine whilst she not only dealt with the grief of losing her child, but also contended with her incarceration for a crime that never actually occurred.

- (3) [...] They were also the ones that said, you know, “Everybody says they’re innocent. What you’ve gotta **do** is show them.” I said, “You’re right.” So I, my classification was GED tutor, because **I’d scored** really, really high. So **I started doing** that, and **I took** parenting classes until **I gave birth**. And after **I gave birth**, **I started** into cosmetology classes and in the evenings **I was taking** Blackstone paralegal course and **volunteering** in the little library. So I can, theoretically, be away from my cell from 5 a.m. to 11 p.m. And so I made sure I was, I was either at work, I was at school, **I was doing** something. Just continuously. When college classes started up, **I signed up** for college classes and got my associates and bachelor’s degree through Ball State, **continued working** in a law library. **Started training** dogs. **Got** vet-tech certification, dog training certification, and started learning about fire science. [...]
- (4) [...] And while I’m, you know, learning about this, **I am sending out** letters. I am asking people to help. A lot of people ignore the letters. So **I continued**, just to plug along. [...] **I just continued to work** and **research, do** what **I could do**, stay out of my bed as often as I could [...] so **I took** a late-night cook position and so **I would bake** cookies [...]

As the latter examples illustrate, Kristine draws on material clauses as a means by which to indicate in her discourse that, essentially, she was forced into a situation whereby she had to make herself mentally strong and the way for her to achieve this was to keep herself busy and do anything within her power to change her fate. Furthermore, these findings coincide with what Bock (2009) uncovered about agency and, thus, Kristine choosing to see herself as doing things as opposed to being passive, with minimal material action: that is, Kristine’s self-portrayal is more consistent with a discourse “of resistance and agency” in favour of an alternative discourse “of victimhood and suffering” (Bock 2009: 14). It also becomes clear that, for the most part, Kristine reflects on her time in prison as a time in which, whilst trying to prove her innocence, she was in large part working on her own. This was markedly so in the earlier years of her incarceration when, for example, many of the letters that she sent out requesting help went unanswered. Although not explicitly appraising herself, then, the types of actions that Kristine describes herself doing are those that, after hearing or reading about her miscarriage of justice, would lead many people to feel admiration and respect for her strength of

character and willpower to never give up¹⁰. Lastly, it is worthwhile noting that a shift from the simple past tense to the present continuous in example (4) above also suggests that Kristine, when talking about her time in prison, simultaneously relives it as if she were transported back there in the present moment.

In addition to placing herself in *Actor* position whilst discussing her time in prison, Kristine, albeit far less frequently, assigns herself the role of *Goal* and, on occasion, *Beneficiary*, as illustrated in examples (5) and (6) below. It is worthwhile remarking on the difference in frequency between Kristine as *Actor* and as *Goal* or *Beneficiary* because her participant role selections serve as a further means to emphasise her commendable activity whilst she was wrongfully imprisoned.

- (5) [...] She got my paperwork. And she **processed** me in, and I went to intake. And so, at the intake dorm, that's where they decide on your classification. What prison you'll be transferred to if you're gonna work. You do some testing to see where your IQ level is. And you meet with a shrink. So, I did all that. They decided I was going to remain there at IVVP because that's where they **keep** the pregnant women. And my, my first little bit in intake was horrible because, of course, they had passed out newspaper clippings of my crime, my case. And so, everybody was waiting for me. And so, several of the women, you know, **shoulder-bumped** me and said, "Look out in the shower, because we're gonna make sure you don't have another baby to hurt." And the guard **put** me in the room, **locked** me up in there. She didn't even **let** me go out to go to the bathroom. [...]
- (6) [...] And so, during this you could feel a change, because now **I'm not being handcuffed and shackled** to go out for breaks. The guard **is bringing** me bottled water along with the prosecutor's table. [...]

Example (5) serves to show how Kristine represents both authority figures as well as those who are, in fact, law breakers; that is, without having to use specific adjectives to describe these people, she leaves us with a clear idea of what they must be like through describing their actions of cruelty. That said, example (6) also shows Kristine's ability to acknowledge that her treatment did actually improve over time and especially by the time her case reached a retrial, suggesting that whilst Kristine was let down by the system, she somehow continues to believe that there are still good people among those who hold a degree of authority.

Finally, we turn to explore Kristine's discussion of her release from prison. In this stage she also cites herself as *Actor* fairly frequently. The examples at this point demonstrate that Kristine most often describes all of the things that she is now able to do or that have changed since she was sent to prison, as in (7), or otherwise, things that she will now need to do or plan out as an everyday citizen in society, as in (8).

- (7) [...] And that was how **I bought** all my clothes. My brother picked them out first, and if they fit good and were comfortable, **I got** them. And then by the time we got out from there, he was like, "Why don't you **put** the bags in the trunk, and we'll go someplace else." And I was like, "Okay." So I'm like this. And he's said, "What do you want?" And I said, "The keys, so **I can get in** the trunk." And he said, so he pushes a button – here comes the trunk! And I was like, "That's fabulous! When did that happen?" So **I put** everything in the trunk and then he takes me over to this little wine place. And so **I got to taste** some wine. [...]
- (8) [...] But, I mean, once you get out and that initial 'woo-woo' passes, then you're caught in this, you know, this cyclone of everything that you want, everything you hope for, everything you dream for, and the reality of what you can afford, and what you can have, and what you can

¹⁰ See example (13) below, for instance.

do. And at 39 years old, going into debt for law school with no guarantee of a job is not something that I needed to be thinking about. Instead, I needed to be thinking about, you know, “How am I **gonna be taking care** of my 16-year-old son? How **am I gonna put** a roof over his head? How **am I gonna clothe** him? How am I gonna make sure he’s got college money?” And then I don’t have any retirement. **I haven’t paid** into social security, so I’m not gonna have anything. I need to start thinking about that. And so, it just, it just stacks up. [...]

Through a retelling of her new-found freedom, we as listeners are reminded of just how tough the consequences must be for an innocent person to have all their rights and freedoms taken away. This is further compounded by the fact that we are being told the story of what happened by a first-hand witness, which serves to reinforce the sense of reality and vividness of the story (Edwards & Potter 1992, as cited in De Fina & Georgakopoulou 2012: 137). Lastly, we also gain some insight into the fact that there is a lack of support for a person who is released from prison due to an overturned conviction.

We now turn our attention to the second most frequent process type, verbal processes with its associated *Sayer* role. Kristine appears as *Sayer* in 29.8% of verbal processes. Furthermore, when this occurs, there appear to be two key themes that surface, namely for Kristine to explain how she maintained her innocence throughout the earlier stages of her ordeal, when being interrogated by police, as in (9) and (10) below; this is something that Kristine never wavered on, despite being tempted to do so in return for her freedom and to have the chance to see her second child grow up¹¹.

(9) [...] He asked me, “Did I start the fire? Did I kill my child? Is there any reason that I would start the fire?” **I answer** each one of those and of course, while he’s asking them you know, one time it was like he’s right here. And so, I jerk, because you know, he sounded so far away. And then all of a sudden he’s loud and in my ear, and the next time I’m straining to try to hear what he’s saying. So he asked me those three questions and then he starts taking everything off and says, “I don’t have to ask any more.” He said, “I know that you did this.” And he said, “You just need to tell me.” And I looked at him and **I said**, “No, that can’t be all of this test.” And he said, “Yes,” he said, “It is. [...]

(10)[...] **I said**, “So there’s no door on his bedroom.” And he said, “Are you sure? Because we have several statements that say **you say** that he was locked in.” And **I said**, “Yeah, **I don’t, I didn’t say** that.” And he said, “Are you sure **you didn’t say** that?” And **I said**, “I don’t know.” And he said, “But, is it possible, because it seems like at the hospital you were really out of it.” “You’re right, I don’t remember saying that.” So after you read that two people said **you said** something you think, “Okay, **I really did**,” and, “I just don’t remember it.” So then when we start going through it again, **I say**, “And I guess **I told** those two people on the way to the ambulance that he was locked in his bedroom and I couldn’t get to him.” And so that was used against me later because there I just changed my story. But it wasn’t in the original telling [...]

A second theme that emerges is for Kristine to remark on the type of behaviours engaged in by police whilst she was under suspicion and trying to deal with the tragic loss of her 3-year-old son, as in (11), as well as the treatment she received from the guards throughout her time in prison, as in (12).

(11)[...] My favourite artist at the time was Bon Jovi and the song was “Always”, but <<FBAT>> called it the ‘I will Always Love You’ song. And all he could sing with me was the chorus and it always says, “I love you, always.” And so that was our song. And he said, “Yes, you can play whatever you want.” He said, “We’ll just need to get a recording of it,” and my dad said, “We’ll

¹¹ As briefly touched upon in the Introduction of this paper, false guilty pleas are rife among innocent people who are so terrified of what might happen that they are willing to do or say anything to avoid a potentially guilty verdict and much harsher sentence at trial.

get a recording,” and he said, “That’s fine.” And they asked who was gonna officiate it and my mom knew some minister who was gonna come in and officiate and **I said** that’s fine because I didn’t really go to church. And so we left there and we went over to the store so I could pick out an outfit to wear for the funeral and the burial and to pick up some clothes that I needed. And that’s when I noticed the police were following us, because I saw them in the store. And **I said**, “What are they doing here?” And my dad said, “They’ve been following.” And **I said**, “Okay. Okay. I don’t really understand why they are but okay.” [...]

(12)[...] And so about 10 o’clock that night I’m knocking on the door. I’ve been in there for four hours and **I’m asking** to use the bathroom. And she wouldn’t open the door. And so my bunkie said, by the time two o’clock rolled around, she was like, “I have an empty Kool-Aid jar.” She said, “It’s, you know, it’s not ideal, but” she said, “I understand being pregnant.” And **I said** okay, so I used a kool-aid jar. And the next morning, 6 o’clock in the morning, the next shift had come on. So the door finally gets open, and we go out to go to breakfast right after the door opens. And I’m standing in line, and I pass out. And so the guard goes with me over to the infirmary and she asks me if I’m trying to hurt my baby. And I started crying and **I tell** her, “No I’m just trying to make it.” **I said**, “I’m doing everything I can.” And she said, “Then why didn’t...” She said, “The nurse says that your blood sugar just bottomed-out.” She said, “Why didn’t you eat your snack.” And **I said**, “What snack? I wasn’t given a snack.” And she said, “Pregnant women are to have a snack.” And **I said**, “I wasn’t given one.” **I said**, “But that guard,” **I said**, “She didn’t even let me go out to go to the bathroom.” **I said**, “There’s a Kool-Aid jar in my room with my urine in it.” And she was like, “What?” And **I said**, “Yes. As soon as I got there I was locked up and I haven’t been out.” [...]

Each of the above examples show Kristine as *Sayer* on several occasions, thus serving as the basis for her to quote her own voice directly. This simultaneously gives her narrative added authenticity, given that it is suggestive of how clearly she remembers the events that took place and, at the same time, Kristine is able to take the narratee right back there with her. Furthermore, the surrounding co-text enables her to suggest the harassment or poor treatment that she faced during the lead up to her wrongful arrest as well as whilst she was serving her prison sentence: that is, example (11) offers us ostensibly verbatim insights into the fact that whilst Kristine should have been focussed on the arrangements for her son’s funeral and allowed to grieve for her child, she was instead subject to regular police harassment. In example (12), we learn how Kristine is indirectly accused of neglecting her second unborn child whilst in prison, when in fact, as any mother would, she is simply trying to survive in her new surroundings. Lastly, both examples lead us to appreciate the genuine sadness and despair that Kristine must have felt after losing her son in such tragic circumstances, which once again is not what one would expect of someone who had intended to kill their child.

Having examined the two most frequent process types across Kristine’s discourse, we now shift our attention briefly to the relational and mental process categories, which although appearing less often (see Figure 1 above), nonetheless merit discussion. Relational processes emerge as the third most frequent type in the dataset, with more than 90% of these comprising relational attributive clauses so this will be our focus of the following discussion. When Kristine is positioned as *Carrier*, the relational attributive processes tend to (i) reference Kristine’s feelings, primarily about herself, as in (13), with her looking for clarification as to why any of this has happened at all; meanwhile, example (14) is a perfect echo of the well-known expression “Don’t judge a book by its cover”, whereby Kristine shows just how important and influential appearances can be when deciding on a person’s guilt or innocence at trial or, at least, that is what her original defence lawyer told her as we witness below.

(13)[...] But it was also because I grew up in church, and so I felt like when I lost <<FBAT>> that God had punished me for something that I did. I didn’t know. I didn’t know what I had done. And then it was like he said, “No.” He said, “You’re not good enough to be a mom.” So

discovering that **I was** pregnant was like, “He’s not saying that. He’s just saying that **I couldn’t** be a mom to that one.” So I started paying attention. I met with my lawyer to go over things [...]

(14)[...] So at this point we’re preparing for trial. He lets me know that all of my family have been put on the witness list, so they cannot come to the courtroom with me. And that’s when he told me, you know, “**My hair was** too big” and, “**It’s** too blonde,” and “And can I tone it down,” and, “Pull it back” and, “Does **it have to be** so frizzy” and, “**My eye-makeup is** oftentimes too dark” and, “Can I not just wear any of that,” and, “Can I wear neutral colours,” and, “Nothing real flashy” and, “Can I not show any throat,” or, and, “Heaven forbid cleavage. That is just out.” He said, “They already look at you as a party girl because **you’re** a single mom,” he said, “So we don’t wanna give them more ammunition.” And he said, “And you don’t react.” And I looked at him and said, “To what?” And he said, “To anything.” He said, “I don’t care what they say.” He said, “You don’t react to anything.” [...]

What emerges in example (14) coincides very closely with what Eades (2010: 191) found in a study of lawyers who advised their clients on how to sit during court cases, arguing that “it is the judge, not the law that really counts”; that is, if the judge takes a dislike to a defendant purely based on personal characteristics, whether this be their personality traits or physical attributes, this may well impact their fate, which appears to be what Kristine’s original defence team was also saying. If this is in fact what occurs, then this finding in itself is a worrying factor for future work on wrongful convictions.

Lastly, to briefly remark on the mental processes encountered in Kristine’s discourse, the majority of cases were found to be mental cognitive, mental desiderative followed by mental perceptive, as in (15) and (16) below.

(15)[...] And so I picked up a pillow and a blanket and I tried to smother it because **I remembered hearing** something that you could smother flames and they would go out. And that absolutely didn’t happen – the pillow and the blanket just melted in my hands. And, of course, **I’m looking** towards where **I know** his bed is and **I think I see** him and **I feel** like, you know, he’s right there I just have to get in that room and I have to, I have to get him. And so, **I think** that **I hear** him, and **I think** that **I see** him, but I can’t get in through that doorway. [...]

(16)[...] So, it was a fifty-thousand-dollar bond. My family could put up five thousand cash and I could walk out. They put up the money and I walked out. And it wasn’t ideal when I walked out, because of course **I’m thinking**, “I have nothing. I have this hanging over my head and **I just want** to be numb.” So, **I was** drinking a lot and taking a lot of pills and **not really focusing** on anything. **I didn’t wanna** feel, **I didn’t wanna** do anything. And after a few days of doing that, I started getting really sick. And – went to the doctor, and that’s when **I discovered** that I was pregnant with <<FBAW>>¹². And that was like the lightbulb that goes off that, “Hey I’ve gotta fight.” [...]

As illustrated in examples (14) and (15), Kristine speaks in the first person and, thus, is frequently the *Senser* of a mental clause. In example (14), Kristine describes how she struggled to be sure of what had actually happened on the night of the fire. Meanwhile, in (15), she details her desire to be left alone and lose all sense of feeling. Both these findings, from a psychological perspective confirm what other research has shown about the primary responses one has to trauma, including displays of avoidance (cf. Carlson & Dalenberg 2000: 11-12) and cognitive impairment or, otherwise, forgetfulness (cf. van Der Kolk 2002), presumably for self-preservation purposes.

¹² <<FBAW>> is the code assigned to Kristine’s second son for anonymity purposes.

With the latter, we draw this subsection to a close and in section 4.2 continue to explore how Kristine represents others who, in one way or another, are involved or, arguably, accountable for her wrongful conviction.

4.2. Which discursive roles does Kristine assign to others who, in one way or another, were involved or accountable for her wrongful conviction?

In order to explore the roles assigned by Kristine to other participants who, in one way or another, were involved or even accountable for her miscarriage of justice, we first revisit material and verbal processes and begin by exploring who else in her discourse is assigned the role of *Actor* or *Sayer*. On closer inspection, the findings show that, in addition to her own actions that fateful night, Kristine discusses the actions of her friends and family as she proceeds to tell me her story, beginning with what they did during the initial stages of her investigation by the police, as in (17) below.

(17)[...] It never occurred to me that he wasn't coming out alive. So, I went to the hospital and when I got there my dad and my brother, who **were waiting** to meet me at the emergency room, and I started telling my dad, immediately, that I needed to be put in a room with <<FBAT>> and I just needed to stay there with him and take care of him. And I knew it would probably be a process, but just to make sure that they put us in the same room. And my dad looked at me and said, "<<FBAT>>, <<FBAT>> didn't make it out alive. He's not gonna be in the hospital." And I couldn't really process that, and so I'm just looking at him and I, I can't say anything and of course you know your mind is saying, "That's not true, that can't be true." And a police officer walked in and said he wanted to take my statement about the fire. And so I tried to sit up and tell him, "Oh yes, sir. I'm happy to give you a statement." And my dad stepped in front of him and **said**, "No. She's not, she's not ready to give a statement. You need to wait. She hasn't even been admitted to the hospital yet. You need to wait." [...]

To add to the latter, example (18) is an indication of how Kristine's brother once again plays a vital role in her life when she is finally released from prison, having been found innocent of any wrongdoing. Moreover, we once again observe how the verbal processes serve as the basis for bringing listeners and readers metaphorically closer to the action.

(18)[...] And he said, "Okay." He said, "What else do you need." I said, "I need high jeans." And so he took me into a super Walmart. And I remember when I walked in and said, "Holy hell! There's beer in Walmart?" He said, "There's everything in Walmart now. They sell it all." So we're going up and down and he said, "You need?" And I said, "I need shampoo and conditioner." And he said, "What kind?" And I said, "Well, I don't know, we had Suave, VO-5, or Pantene in there." I said, "I don't want any of that. But there's a whole aisle!" And he said, "Well what do you want it to do?" And I said, "I want to smell pretty. Nothing really smells good in there." So he went up and down the aisle with me smelling stuff until we found something that smelled really pretty. And it went in the cart. By the time we were getting through there, and I said, you know, "I'm gonna need tampons." We get to a whole wall of tampons, and he says, "What kind do you use?" And, of course, by this time I'm just done. And I shrugged, and here comes a tear down my cheek. And he says, "You know what? My wife uses this." And he puts it in the cart. He said, "If you don't like it, we'll come back tomorrow and get a different kind." And he said, "We'll come back every day until you know what your kind is." And I said, "Okay." [...]

As evidenced in each of the aforementioned examples, then, through a combination of references to her family members as *Actor* or *Sayer*, Kristine portrays a very positive and supportive picture of her immediate family members. Kristine's family are seen to offer unwavering support, both during the

aftermath of her son's death as well as on her release from prison when she is forced to adapt to a very different world from the one she had lived in prior to her incarceration in 1996. That is, as listeners, we come to realise how basic and shielded prison life is and, thus, how overwhelming it must be to leave and not have knowledge of everyday things that most of us simply take for granted.

Also portrayed in a very positive light are the defence lawyers who represented Kristine at her retrial, with a notable number of verbal processes emerging, as illustrated in example (19).

(19)[...] So, my lawyer gets up there and she was talking, you know, *she said* "you had a very confused victim that you were talking to" and *she said* "I am 100% sure that <<FBAT>> was dead before the flames ever broke out, before his mother ever woke up". And *she said*, "That's because he got to an 80% carboxy hemoglobin." *She said*, "Which means, usually, blood bonds with oxygen." *She said*, "In this case it was bonding with carbon monoxide." So, *she said*, "His mother, who is in the very next room, is breathing in carbon monoxide as well." *She said*, "So if he's at 80," *she said*, "She's at least 35-40." So, *she said*, "Roughly around 30," *she said*, "You feel inebriated." *She said*, "She could have been hallucinating." *She said*, "She could have felt like she was doing everything right." And *she said*, "And she was absolutely standing still." *She said*, "We don't know." *She said*, "What we do know, is the basic facts of what she said every single time: I did this, I went here, I did this, I tried to get in here." *She said*, "That's all the same. Every single time." So, *she said*, "She did do that." *She said*, "Do we know how fast she did it? Do we know what her mindset was when she did it? No. But we know she did those basic things. She busted out her window, she tried to get in there. She tried to put the fire out in the door." *She said*, "One of the neighbours said he had a nervous breakdown because every time he closed his eyes, he could hear her screams." *She said*, "So we know she's doing all those things." *She said*, "Those extra steps that you threw in," *she said*, "about the door being blocked." *She said*, "You know, did she go buy something, and her story changing." *She said*, "**I am not gonna tell** this mother that her baby didn't wake her up and get her out to safety." And *she said*, "**I'm just not.**" And *she said*, "I'm not even a mother," but *she said*, "The thought of that breaks my heart." So, *she said*, "I would never do that." *She said*, "Do I believe that that happened?" *She said*, "Scientifically, no." *She said*, "He was gone." *She said*, "So," *she said*, "You're playing on her fear, her loss." *She said*, "Her shock. Her injuries. All of that." [...]

Through assigning her defence team the role of *Sayer* repeatedly, as seen in the above example, Kristine is able to convey her story to the listener through the voice of those with a high degree of authority, thus not only ensuring that the truth is heard, but that what she is relaying is given added credibility. That is, if a professional is convinced by what Kristine is saying and, moreover, given the opportunity to explain the factual evidence of this case as was the case at Kristine's retrial, it was always more likely that a jury would believe Kristine's version of events. To add to the latter, Kristine is able to reiterate the mistreatment she endured whilst under investigation by the local police through the voice of her defence team; that is, above we observe how her defence lawyers imply the fabrication of evidence (i.e. "Those extra steps you threw in, she said, about the door being blocked") on the part of police, insinuating that the original investigation was a clear case of tunnel vision and, to a degree, corrupt, without having to explicitly state as much. Thus, although Kristine already referenced police tactics with herself as *Sayer*, her claims are given additional weighting the second time round simply because they were voiced by those with a far higher degree of authority and power in the legal context.

To return briefly to the use of material clauses in combination with verbal clauses, the actions and utterances of other participants, including those who work for the emergency services, the prison and the police force are also cited in Kristine's discourse. Furthermore, with a number of cases of the police in particular referenced as *Actor* of a material clause and/or *Sayer* of a verbal clause, it is worthwhile noticing how their representation seems to alter as the interview progresses, with examples in the initial phase (i.e. the narrative the night of the fire) seemingly neutral. However, from the moment

Kristine describes that she was under suspicion right up until talking about the time she spent in prison, we see a shift towards a notably more negative portrayal of those in authority through the actions they take or the things that they say, as illustrated in (20) below.

(20)[...] And we go for the funeral and then after the service we go over to the cemetery and we have the burial and the police are there. They went to the service, and they followed us to the cemetery. And so, at that time, I'm feeling like I haven't even had a moment to process what's happened to my baby, to me, to my life, what it means, what it looks like, and every time I turn around here are these people reminding me of something else. So I walked up to them and said, "What is it gonna take? What is it gonna take for you to not be here? I don't want to see you again, I don't want to be reminded again. I just want you to go away." And he said, "Would you agree to a polygraph?" And I said, "Yes, absolutely. If it gets rid of you, yes." [...]

Unlike the depiction of her family and friends, then, those in authority who in some way or another were involved or accountable for Kristine's wrongful conviction are portrayed in a rather negative light. That is, in example (20) above, Kristine again explains how the police were, essentially, harassing her at a time when what should have been her sole concern was to grieve for her son and give him the send-off he deserved. Similarly, such unjust treatment at the hands of those supposedly working to ensure societal justice merely serves to portray the police as showing anything but fair and reasonable behaviour towards Kristine, matching the image presented earlier of prison guards (see example (12) above), when one evening in prison, several months pregnant and desperate to use the bathroom, the prison guards on duty deliberately ignored Kristine's request to use the toilet. Thus, through her discourse and, more specifically, the transitivity patterns employed in Kristine's narrative, we see how she draws on the actions and things that were done or said to her in order to focus our attention on the types of treatment she faced during her ordeal with the justice system, which time and time again seemed to work against her.

Additional evidence from the transitivity findings to suggest a negative portrayal of those in a position of authority is also provided by the relational and mental processes used by Kristine in her discourse. The former, for instance, serve to show how the police decided, no more than three questions into her lie detector test, that Kristine was guilty of arson and the murder of her three-year-old son, whilst the latter show them openly insulting Kristine during questioning, all of which is illustrated in (21) below.

(21)[...] He said, "I know that you did this." And he said, "You just need to tell me." And I looked at him and I said, "No, that can't be all of this test." And he said, "Yes," he said, "It is. I've been doing this a long time" he said, "So I know that you did this. You just need to tell me." And I said, "I don't know that I did this. I don't know. So I have nothing to tell you." And he said, "No." You know, he said, "This machine doesn't lie." He said, "It's been used over and over again, you just need to tell me the truth." And I said, "I'm telling you the truth. I don't know that I did this. I don't know." And he said, "You are one sick and twisted bitch." And so he said, "You've just gotta be sick." And so I looked at him and said, "I may be sick, I may be twisted. Get me a doctor, get me a lawyer, but get out of my face." And, of course, by that time we're both loud. [...]

In the above example, the assertiveness conveyed through the verb *know* in the affirmative proves particularly powerful because when uttered by someone such as the police, the likelihood is that we doubt ourselves before doubting the word of the police; that is, as the interviewee (or even as a member of the general public), one might tend to assume that the police do not lie and that they do not make mistakes. Therefore, through talking about what the police allegedly knew, we understand just how difficult it would have been for Kristine to counter-argue what she was being told. Furthermore, in contrast to the police, Kristine also demonstrates a lack of assertiveness through her negation of the

verb *know* when used in the first person, thereby suggesting she really wasn't sure about what happened or, at least, less sure than the investigating police officers, and was perhaps unsurprisingly deemed an unreliable witness. All that said, by looking beyond clause level and instead at a series of clauses in combination and "the semantic resources that lead us from one clause to another" (Martin & Rose 2007: 1), example (21) succeeds in conveying a negative picture of authority figures and not of Kristine herself; that is, in Kristine's discourse it quickly becomes apparent that there exists a gross imbalance of power between the interviewing police officer(s) and Kristine, as the interviewee whilst inside the police station, not to mention the fact that the police resort to cruel remarks as part of the interrogation process. Therefore, the stretch of discourse as a whole invites the listener to recognise that those with the questionable morals are, in fact, the police, in this instance.

Lastly, it is worthwhile citing an example in Kristine's discourse which serves to convey a rather negative image of the judge at her original trial. Moreover, example (22) below continues to reinforce the idea just described in relation to the degree of assertiveness exhibited by authority figures.

(22)[...] The jury was dismissed and then my judge sentences me, and he said, "*I see* you have gotten yourself impregnated in order to gain sympathy from this court, and that absolutely will not happen. That child will become a ward of the state and you will never lay eyes on him." And he said, "I am sentencing you 60 years for murder, 50 for arson, and I'm gonna run them concurrently." Now I didn't know that 'concurrently' meant that they were merged, and I just heard, "You're taking my baby and you just sentenced me to 110 years." [...]

Through the use of a mental cognitive process (i.e. *see*), the judge is seen here as assertive and perhaps even ruthless in his final remarks. It is important to note, however, that positioning the judge in the role of *Senser* in this example is not, at least on its own, what conveys the highly negative meaning that inevitably comes across; rather, the adverse meanings derive largely from the projected language in the clause, including the unusual relational clause structure you have gotten yourself impregnated (*Attributor-Carrier-Attribute*) together with the hypotactic clause of purpose (i.e. in order to gain sympathy), thus again manifesting how meanings are generated beyond word and individual clause level (Martin & Rose 2007). However, the *Senser* role is still rather powerful here because it gives the judge, as with the police in the previous example, the status of knower and, in light of his already authoritative status in the legal arena, makes it very difficult if not impossible for Kristine to dispute.

Thus, overall, we witness how a transitivity analysis of Kristine's discourse constructs a negative portrayal of those in a position of authority, both in the lead up to her original trial as well as whilst serving a sentence for a crime that she never committed. This, of course, is to be expected in light of the fact that they put her through a terrible ordeal and, moreover, have never been held accountable for doing so. It is also clear in Kristine's discourse that she is able to reflect on her miscarriage of justice quite positively, in particular when discussing the help that she received from both her immediate family members and the defence team who worked on her retrial, eventually winning her appeal and proving her innocence.

5. Conclusion

The application of a transitivity analysis to the discourse of Kristine has made it possible to acquire insights into how a wrongful conviction can impact primarily the exoneree, but also others involved, e.g. their loved ones. In analysing Kristine's discourse, we can observe whose actions, feelings, thoughts and whose voice comes to the forefront, and consider why this may be the case. At the root of transitivity "is the belief that participants could have spoken otherwise, that a range of choices is open to a writer or speaker and that any text could conceivably have been produced in a different way" (Footitt 2002: 89). In this case, the transitivity resources are frequently used to convey a sense of close proximity to the events and the sayings of the participants, particularly through direct projection.

Although there are a number of studies which have investigated the use of language inside the courtroom, whether it be for a wrongful conviction case (cf. Bartley 2018, 2020) or otherwise (cf. Stygall 1994; Statham 2016), as well as a number of studies that examine how certain traumatic experiences (e.g. sexual assault, domestic violence survivors) are represented linguistically (cf. Bletzer & Koss 2010; Neuman Allen & Wozniak 2010; Levy & Eckhaus 2020), how the wrongfully convicted represent their miscarriage of justice linguistically is, to my knowledge, previously unexplored. Thus, the current paper is designed to serve as a departure point and, consequently, contribute to filling the current research gap in this area.

To briefly review the transitivity findings from the interview with Kristine, what we observe is that Kristine is one of the main *Actors* as well as *Sayers* throughout her discourse. This is perhaps unsurprising given that Kristine is asked to narrate the on-goings of her wrongful conviction, which of course, she is at the centre of and, therefore, is often seen to use the first-person singular *I*, to retell her story. Nevertheless, she does this in such a way that makes it clear she could not be guilty of any wrongdoing because the actions she took are not those typical of an arsonist or murderer. Furthermore, Kristine seems to construe herself in the same way that other survivors of injustice have done so: that is, in the same way that testimonies from activists revealed (cf. Bock 2009), Kristine also represents herself as very active, regardless of how adverse the circumstances may be.

In addition to describing her own actions, Kristine also refers to the actions of her immediate family very positively. That is, her parents and her brother are seen to offer unconditional support and provide help both during the initial investigation as well as following her release. Meanwhile, when Kristine instead discusses the actions or thoughts of those in a position of authority, we witness a notable difference in their portrayal. Firstly, the transitivity analysis reveals a higher number of references to negative action, leaving the listener rather perturbed on hearing the behaviour of the police and, subsequently, the prison guards who were involved in her miscarriage of justice. In addition, those in authority are portrayed as particularly assertive, but this again serves to paint them in a negative light; that is, the principle of "innocent until proven guilty" seemingly did not apply to Kristine's case. Instead, what comes through in her discourse is that Kristine was presumed guilty from the beginning. It is important to highlight this because, although on the surface it may seem that the main cause of Kristine's wrongful conviction was faulty science, hence her wrongful conviction for arson, it also becomes apparent that tunnel vision most likely played a role here. Lastly, the findings from Kristine's discourse also draw our attention to another separate, yet related issue regarding societal expectations. Through Kristine's use of relational processes, she draws our attention towards the importance of a woman's personal appearance in court and how this alone may shape what society considers will constitute the guilt or innocence of a given individual (cf. Eades 2010).

With the latter comes a potential future avenue of research, i.e. to see, either via additional interviews with other female exonerees or through an analysis of the media coverage of those who have been through a trial by media (cf. Statham 2016), whether a person's appearance could have played a role in their wrongful conviction. A second research avenue could include analysing more interviews with exonerees to determine if the transitivity patterns found here are similar or different across interviews and whether these patterns align with other interviews of people relating other types of trauma. Finally, it would be interesting to apply other linguistic frameworks, from within and beyond SFG (e.g. Appraisal) (cf. Martin & White 2005; Bednarek 2008; Benítez-Castro & Hidalgo-Tenorio 2019), for triangulation purposes and, thus, further explore the findings thus far regarding discursive representation of those involved in wrongful conviction cases.

To conclude, through an analysis of the transitivity patterns in a semi-structured interview with exoneree Kristine, the current paper has provided insights into how, through her discourse, Kristine represents her miscarriage of justice, her response while imprisoned and those involved in her wrongful conviction. Studies such as this one are paramount, not only because they enable survivors of a traumatic experience to be heard, but because they serve to draw attention to an issue that is particularly problematic in society and, yet, largely below the radar of public consciousness. As outlined above, wrongful convictions are notably more frequent than generally acknowledged. Although the

estimate of innocent people in prison may seem low at first glance, at 3-4%, this means that of 100,000 inmates in the US prison system alone, 3,000-4,000 are factually innocent and serving a prison sentence for no reason other than that the system got it wrong.

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Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Kristine Bunch for her extraordinary generosity and never-wavering strength, which has contributed so much to our understanding of the experience of exonerees. I would also like to thank the reviewers who provided such helpful and constructive feedback on previous versions of this article. I am ever so grateful. Lastly, I would like to thank my father, John Bartley, my brother Nathan and my sister Sam for their never-ending unconditional support, as well as my friends and colleagues, Lucas Chambers, Encarnación Hidalgo-Tenorio and Maite Taboada for their constant encouragement, warmth and guidance whilst I worked on aspects of this paper.

Funding

The research reported in this article has been conducted under the auspices of the project 'Transitivity in Courtroom Language: A Unified System' (TICLAUS). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 838444.